

THE ENHANCEMENT OF CRITICAL THINKING THROUGH INTEGRATION OF OTHER SUBJECTS

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“It is high time you changed your way of teaching, moving forward with novelty rather than traditional ones”. This type of advice is always in the mouth of ESL trainers while holding training sessions in Uzbekistan. Indeed, it is true. There is a lot of reformation being done in the field of the educational system of Uzbekistan by the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education in association with the Ministry of Public Education. Changing the approaches of a teacher brings a great challenge as an educator should be impressed to get risks in the classroom. Whereas the generation, who is ambitious to chase technology, an educator should make good use of it. The existence of swapping digital knowledge gives a far better chance to enhance critical thinking abilities, which can be done through integration of other subjects, to illustrate that in practice some observation has been done in the example of mathematical and biological paths. Teacher trainer statistics observed in-service teachers at educational divisions in Tashkent city, accumulating only a small number of teachers implementing integrative approaches to increase critical thinking abilities while learning a language. In this sense, this article is going to illustrate and share a summary of integrative methods while learning a language with laying out cases with different grades at school.

Key words: integration, learning a language, mathematical approach, student, critical thinking, CLIL, biological approach.

Educational institutions are the place where a learner should obtain necessary skills to become one of essential aide in various careers and areas. Learning a language is beneficial as well as promotional as it is always learnt in integration. Furthermore, the subject of language learning is included in every educational institution which boosts the chance of enforcing the way students evaluate, analyze and develop a doubtful thinker with the help of combination of other themes. Incorporation of other fields into a language learning can be done with the CLIL method which demands a collaboration with other subjects. The authors of the article **The CLIL method as a new educational technology** Tamara V. Agapova and Larisa Yu. Aisner site that CLIL considers learning a foreign language as a tool for learning other subjects, thus forming students' need for studying, which allows them to develop their abilities in communication, including his native language. This is the most common definition: CLIL is a didactic method that allows students to form linguistic and communicative foreign language competences in the same learning context, when they form and acquire general educational knowledge and skills. In this regard, an educator is considered to be a main incentive to develop, train and learn skills to be able to get the learners to acquire combined knowledge of various subject areas while learning a foreign language. One of the most functional subject areas to expand student critical thinking abilities is mathematics. Dr Tristha Ramamurthy gives his opinion in his article named “Importance of 'Mathematical Thinking': Simple steps to develop this skill as following “Mathematics is how you see the world around you. It is a subject that proposes elegant solutions while also

offering infinite possibilities to pose new questions. Therefore, an attempt can be made to map all situations and problems in everyday life to relevant mathematical models to solve them”

According to C. Evanc, Measuring Student Success Skills; instructional strategies develop critical thinking skills by allowing students to solve problems, using open-ended questions and providing various learning activities to engage students in solving those problems.

Practical research

This approach was briefly addressed to the third-grade learners at Specialized school № 4 in Tashkent city. The learners used to be filled with the vocabulary of a new topic almost every lesson in the paper form with ready bilingual translation. While putting into practice the CLIL with mathematical approach, students were given numbers with allocated letters. The learners had to look at numbers in the task and chose the letter matching the number. Later they had to use numeric words to make full sentences. Lastly, they had a collection of sentences related to the topic.

Topic: My favorite subject

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18
J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R
19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	
S	T	U	V	W	X	Y	Z	

Find the letters in the table and get the word.

13	1	20	8

1	18	20

16	5

5	14	7	12	9	19	8

Answers: Math, Art, PE, English

The advantage of the mathematical approach with natural numbers with the third-grade learners was being able to increase learner speculation, concentrate and engage totally to the lesson. None of the learners were lost or disturbed by other factors during the instruction and while activity. Moreover, their memorization skills were detected to be increased in the most positive way even with low-achieving learners. The disadvantage of the applied method was time consuming and slow movement from one activity to another. Young learners intensify their activity with further practice, though. Another subject area which was integrated while learning English was Biology. In fact, it was a biology teacher who took the initiative of combining two lessons in one after had been told about integrative research in our school. There was a practical experience with the 9th grade students at the same school as the 3rd grade learners. The planning and designing of the lesson were not easy due to the lack of knowledge on biology by an ESL teacher, but active negotiations by both teachers resulted beneficially. One should be mention that the combined lesson was held in the school which is

specialized for disabled learners both physically and ADHD attention deficit hyperactivity disorder, which compels much scaffolding and inclusiveness. The lesson was designed as a form of competition between four small teams. The learners were expected to answer the biology quiz using their brushed English vocabulary.

One of the quizzes was to describe the tongue formulation of a human. The contest participants of the 9th grade were supposed to explain the composition of the tongue in English. As it was mentioned above, the interpretation of tongue system is troublesome even in native language, so expectations seem to be falling, initially. However, the learners showed unanticipated results. Learner autonomy and vocabulary memorization grew up twice as much. Writing and speaking abilities of learners on food adjectives boosted three times more than it was before. Moreover, Biology teacher stated that student understanding of that topic in integration was of higher quality.

Tongue description quiz:

The questions were distributed in paper form to encourage various intelligences while learning. It was analyzed that some of participants watched informative videos, some of them read biology books, others even had a collaboration with science teachers to be accessible for the contest.

1. What taste buds are there in the tongue?
2. Which part of the tongue can taste like sweets?
3. Which part of the tongue is the most sensitive to the better tastes?
4. Which part of the tongue can taste lemon?

To summarize, the practical experience of mathematical and biological integration during English classes illustrated the enhancement and rise of learner motivation. Furthermore, memorization and comprehension of the topic attained through analyzing and investigating the topic, which arose learner autonomy. The learners were given a chance to gain understanding using their abilities and skills to pick up information. Hence, there is a big undivided attention to involve other subject areas while teaching a language, who knows, maybe in the future even someone who is not into a language, will learn it without consciously integrating it with his favorite subject.

References:

1. Dumitru, D. (2019). Creating meaning. The importance of Arts, Humanities and Culture for critical thinking development. *Studies in Higher Education*, 44(5), 870–879.
2. Tamara V. Agapova, Larisa Yu. Aisner The CLIL method as a new educational technology, *Pedagogical Journal*. 2019, Vol. 9. Is. 2A,
3. Natthanon Monrat, Mingkhuan Phaksunchai and Ratchanikorn Chonchaiya Developing Students' Mathematical Critical Thinking Skills Using Open-Ended Questions and Activities Based on Student Learning Preferences, Volume 2022 | Article ID 3300363 | <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/3300363>.

4. S. Syafril, N. R. Aini, Netriwati, A. Pahrudin, N. E. Yaumas, and Engkizar, “Spirit of mathematics critical thinking skills (CTS),” *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, vol. 1467, no. 1, Article ID 012069, 2020. View at: [Publisher Site](#) | [Google Scholar](#)
5. C. Evans, *Measuring Student Success Skills: A Review of the Literature on Critical Thinking*, Center for Assessment, Dover, NH, USA, 2020.
emedicine.medscape.com.

Web sites:

1. <https://www.indiatoday.in/education-today/featurephilia/story/importance-of-mathematical-thinking-simple-steps-to-develop-this-skill-2285689-2022-10-15/>.